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Multiscale simulations of thermal and non-thermal responses of photovoltaic materials to ultrafast x-ray irradiation

Aldo Artímez Peña^{1,2,*} and Nikita Medvedev^{1,3} ¹ Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Na Slovance 1999/2, 182 00 Prague 8, Czech Republic² Higher Institute of Technologies and Applied Sciences, University of Havana, Ave. Salvador Allende 1110, 10 400, La Habana, Cuba³ Institute of Plasma Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Za Slovankou 3, 182 00 Prague 8, Czech Republic

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: pena@fzu.cz**Keywords:** XUV/x-ray ultrafast irradiation, damage thresholds, phase transitions, superionic states, photovoltaic materials, ablation thresholds

Abstract

Lead sulfide (PbS), cadmium telluride (CdTe), and indium tin oxide (ITO) play crucial roles in various electronic applications where laser treatment enables precise modification of their distinctive electronic characteristics. This study utilizes the XTANT-3 hybrid/multiscale model to investigate the microscopic response of these materials to ultrafast x-ray irradiation. The model simultaneously traces intertwined processes of non-equilibrium dynamics of both electrons and atoms, electron–phonon coupling, and nonthermal melting via changes in the interatomic potential induced by the excitation of electrons. Among the materials studied, CdTe exhibits the highest radiation resistance, similar to cadmium sulfide (CdS). At the respective threshold doses, the melting is primarily thermal, driven by electron–phonon coupling, which is accompanied by the band gap closure. Additionally, all materials exhibit nonthermal melting at higher doses. Energy dissipation pathways and material recrystallization increases the damage thresholds substantially. In CdTe and PbS, below 1.5 eV atom^{-1} , the band gap returns to its original value upon recrystallization. As the dose increases, the resulting cooled material becomes increasingly amorphous, progressively reducing the band gap until a stable configuration is reached. Notably, in a narrow window of deposited doses, ITO exhibits transient superionic behavior, with the liquid oxygen but solid indium (In) and tin (Sn) sublattices. At 0.6 eV atom^{-1} in CdTe and 0.4 eV atom^{-1} in PbS and ITO, material ablation from the surface occurs at the ten-picosecond timescale.

1. Introduction

Modern electronic device manufacturing involves a variety of materials. Key semiconductor compounds nowadays include cadmium telluride (CdTe), lead sulfide (PbS), and indium tin oxide (ITO), which have gained prominence across multiple applications, such as photovoltaics [1–3], light-emitting diodes [4, 5], and radiation detectors [6–10]. Zincblende CdTe, the most common phase of this compound, has a direct bandgap of 1.45 eV [11] while PbS is a narrow band gap material (0.41 eV), making it sensitive to infrared light, with thin-film configurations displaying quantum confinement effects [12]. ITO is a tin-doped In_2O_3 -based n-type wide-bandgap semiconductor (4.0 eV) with Sn dopant levels forming below the bottom of the conduction band, making it a nearly optically transparent semiconducting material [1–3].

Laser-based processing is a fundamental approach for semiconductor engineering, machining, and nanopatterning [13, 14]. Laser irradiation induces spatially confined phase transitions in target materials, enabling precise modification of their properties unachievable by any other means. Melting and ablation thresholds under nanosecond-pulse irradiation have been previously documented for CdTe [15, 16]. However, comparable data for PbS or ITO remain unreported in the current literature. Furthermore, high-dose-rate irradiation

(ultrashort intense pulses) may trigger alternative kinetic pathways and produce damage distinct from its low-dose-rate conventional counterpart [17].

Free-electron lasers produce intense femtosecond pulses of extreme ultraviolet (XUV)/x-ray radiation [17–20]. Due to the ultrashort pulse duration, such irradiation achieves extremely high dose rates. It enables the generation and examination of highly nonequilibrium states of matter under extreme conditions [17, 21] and allows for unprecedented control of the material modifications [22]. Recent advances in laser–plasma accelerators pave the way for the development of compact x-ray free-electron laser (XFEL) sources [23–26]. These facilities are expected to significantly broaden the future application of XFEL technology in materials processing [27–32].

The XUV/x-ray spectral range offers important advantages for studying nonequilibrium phase transitions in these materials. In this regime, core–shell photoionization followed by Auger cascades [33, 34] rapidly creates a dense electronic excitation across the entire band structure within the femtosecond pulse duration, providing a cleaner and more controllable route to nonthermal melting [35, 36] than optical irradiation, where reaching comparable excitation densities requires nonlinear effects, such as multiphoton or above-threshold ionization and the associated strong-field effects. Furthermore, since phase transitions are defined primarily by the absorbed energy density rather than the specific photon energy, the present results are not restricted to the XUV/x-ray regime but are transferrable across a wide range of photon energies from NIR or optical to x-rays [37].

Laser interaction with matter involves several distinct stages [38, 39]: Initially, photon absorption by electrons occurs, exciting electrons to high-energy levels in the material. This includes valence-to-conduction band transitions in semiconducting materials. When the photon energy is sufficiently high, i.e., in the case of XUV or x-ray lasers, core–shell photoabsorption is the dominant mechanism, releasing bound electrons to unoccupied states and creating core-level holes. These core holes undergo Auger decay, typically at femtosecond timescales, whereas radiative decay (fluorescence) is much less probable in light elements or outer shells [33, 34].

The excited electrons undergo secondary cascades, generating additional excited electrons via impact ionization, scattering on plasmons, and interacting with atoms and phonons [34, 39]. Electron–electron interaction relaxes the electron distribution function to the equilibrium Fermi–Dirac shape at sub-picosecond timescales.

The atomic lattice receives energy from hot electrons through two main pathways: nonadiabatic electron–ion (or electron–phonon) coupling, typically occurring at picosecond timescales; and adiabatic alterations of the atomic potential energy surface at sub-picosecond timescales. At sufficiently high doses, the latter mechanism may trigger nonthermal melting, disordering the atomic system even without thermal heating [35, 36]. At even higher energy densities, electron-driven modifications of the interatomic potential may accelerate atoms, heating the lattice at femtosecond scales, much faster than the electron–phonon coupling [40]. Such ultrafast out-of-equilibrium processes may create unusual transient material states outside of its phase diagram [41, 42].

This work studies the processes triggered in CdTe, PbS, and ITO by ultrafast intense XUV/x-ray irradiation, determining the respective damage thresholds and mechanisms, and examines transient states produced. These materials, in particular CdTe-based, are used in pixel-array detectors, actively deployed at XFEL beamlines [6–10]. ITO-coated glass substrates constitute the standard working electrode in the *in situ* electrochemical cells used for ambient-pressure x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy and synchrotron-based electrochemical studies [43–46].

2. Methodology

Irradiation of CdTe, PbS, and ITO by femtosecond XUV/x-ray pulses is modelled with a state-of-the-art combined code XTANT-3 [47]. All the above-mentioned processes are modelled with a few coupled simulation modules, interconnected on-the-fly, see its schematics in figure 1 [48]. A comprehensive description of the models and their computational implementation are available in the XTANT-3 manual [49]; below, we briefly describe the relevant physics and the numerical details used in this work.

The absorption of incoming x-ray/XUV photons, subsequent kinetics of the excited electrons, and core-hole Auger decays, are described with event-by-event (analog) transport Monte-Carlo (MC) simulation [48, 50, 51]. The cross sections of photon absorption in various elements, characteristic Auger decay times, and atomic ionization potentials of each electronic orbital are taken from the EPICS2023 database [52]. The MC module traces the electronic cascades as long as the energy of an electron is above the predefined cutoff of 10 eV (counted from the bottom of the conduction band of the material). The impact ionization of core shells and scattering on the valence-band electrons is described within the linear response theory, applying the Ritchie-Howie oscillators model for the complex-dielectric-function (CDF) [53]. The single-pole approximation is used for the CDF oscillators [54]. The elastic scattering of fast electrons is described with the Rutherford cross-

section with the modified Molier screening parameter [50]. Statistical reliability of the MC simulations is ensured by averaging over 50,000 iterations [48, 55].

The distribution function of electrons below the energy cutoff is modelled with the Boltzmann equation. The distribution function defines fractional electron populations on the transient energy levels in the valence and conduction bands.

Instantaneous electron thermalization is assumed for the electron–electron scattering [56]. The applicability of this assumption in the regime studied here is supported by a dedicated analysis in [56], which showed that in semiconductors irradiated at doses near or above the damage threshold, the effect of finite electron–electron thermalization times on the atomic response is relatively mild, shifting the nonthermal damage threshold by at most $\sim 15\%$ when varying the thermalization time within the realistically expected range. Furthermore, at doses above the melting threshold, bandgap collapse leads to metallization of the material (see below), after which electron–electron scattering becomes significantly more efficient, further justifying the approximation at the timescales relevant to the damage dynamics studied here.

The electron–phonon interaction (nonadiabatic coupling) is described with the dynamical coupling approach, using the matrix element calculated from the evolving tight binding (TB) Hamiltonian [57].

The transferable tight-binding method is used to obtain molecular orbitals (electron energy levels or band structure) and interatomic forces [58]. The nonorthogonal TB Hamiltonian depends on the relative coordinates of all atoms in the supercell. The secular equation is solved at each timestep of the simulation, producing the transient electronic states and the atomic potential energy surface. Thus, changes in the electronic distribution function, induced by the pulse, directly affect the interatomic potential, allowing to simulate nonthermal phase transitions. For each material, we employ the periodic table baseline parameters (PTBP) [59, 60], which relies on sp^3d^5 LCAO basis set within the DFTB framework.

Dynamics of the atomic system is simulated with help of the Molecular Dynamics (MD) method. The atomic potential is obtained from the TB method described above. The energy exchange between the electrons and atoms (dynamical electron–phonon coupling) is distributed to the atomic ensemble via velocity scaling algorithm at each MD timestep [57]. The propagation of atomic trajectories is done with the Martyna–Tuckerman 4th order algorithm with a timestep of 1 fs in the microcanonical (NVE) ensemble [61].

In summary, the coupled modules operate within the code interconnectedly and self-consistently as follows: the MC module tracks photon absorption, core-hole Auger decay, and electron cascade until all excited electrons fall below the 10 eV cutoff; the Boltzmann module then evolves the electron distribution; the TB module continuously updates the electronic energy levels and interatomic forces; and the MD module propagates the atomic trajectories under the TB-derived forces (see figure 1) [48].

CdTe and PbS simulations utilize 216-atom supercells constructed from the unit cells from [62]. ITO supercell contains 320 atoms set by randomly replacing 10% of the In atoms with Sn atoms in the In_2O_3

Figure 2. Electron heat capacity as a function of the electronic temperature (T_e) in CdTe, PbS, ITO, as well as CdS and In_2O_3 for comparison, calculated with XTANT-3. The values are close to 0 at low T_e because electrons are bound across the band gap and only become thermally active once T_e is comparable to the gap energy; the sharp rise above $\sim 4,000$ K marks this onset.

structure [62]. These supercell sizes are sufficient for reliable simulations [51]. Periodic boundary conditions are employed to simulate the relevant materials in the bulk.

The methods for the calculation of electronic heat capacity and heat conductivity are detailed in [49, 63], using $7 \times 7 \times 7$ k-point grid. The electronic heat capacity and heat conductivity are deterministically calculated for a given atomic structure and thus carry no statistical uncertainty. The dynamical coupling formalism is used for the evaluation of the electron–ion coupling parameter calculations, averaged over up to 100 independent realizations, with resulting uncertainties on the order of $< 10\%$ (see detailed analysis of the uncertainties in [57]).

Simulations start 200 fs prior FEL pulse arrival, allowing for the atomic equilibration, and continue for 15 ps post-irradiation for ITO and 30 ps for CdTe and PbS supercells (with a gaussian laser pulse centered at 0 fs) [64]. Long-term effects of irradiation (section 3.3) are modelled using Berendsen-like thermostat set at room temperature with 1 ps (1000 fs) characteristic cooling time [49]. Simulations of thin layers (section 3.4) include periodic boundaries along X and Y axis, and free surfaces along Z. All simulations are performed within the microcanonical (NVE) ensemble, except for section 3.3, in which the Berendsen thermostat is employed (NVT ensemble).

All atomic snapshots are visualized with OVITO software [65]. The code XTANT-3 was validated by comparison with available experimental data on the damage thresholds in various materials with a reasonable agreement (see, e.g., [42, 51, 66, 67]).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermodynamic properties

Electron heat capacity, electron heat conductivity, and electron–phonon coupling parameter in CdTe, PbS, ITO (and CdS and pure In_2O_3 for comparison) are calculated with XTANT-3 in steps of 100 K in electron temperature, producing effectively continuous curves, see figures 2–3. These are key parameters in thermodynamic modeling of laser irradiation, such as the two-temperature model and its derivatives [57, 68, 69].

As typical for semiconductors [69], the electronic heat capacity is near zero at the electron temperatures below the values comparable with the bandgap, see figure 2. Above $T_e \sim 4,000$ K, the heat capacity rises sharply in all the materials studied.

The materials under study exhibit low electronic heat conductivity (figure 4) compared to other semiconductors [63]. The maximum values of this parameter for PbS and ITO are within the range typically observed for metals; moreover, the electronic heat conductivity as a function of temperature is similar to that in elemental Pb [63]. It is significantly lower in CdS and CdTe and almost independent of the temperature at values above 15,000 K (figure 4).

As shown in figure 3, the electron–phonon coupling is strongest in ITO, in line with the previous observation that lighter elements typically couple to electrons more efficiently than heavier ones (e.g., compare CdS versus CdTe) [57, 69].

Figure 3. Electron–phonon (electron–ion) coupling in CdTe, PbS, ITO, CdS, and In_2O_3 for comparison, calculated with XTANT-3. Coupling is strongest in ITO and weakest in CdTe, because this parameter controls the rate of energy transfer from hot electrons to the lattice, this ordering correlates inversely with the resistance to thermal damage.

Figure 4. Electron heat conductivity as a function of electronic temperature in CdTe, PbS, ITO, CdS, and In_2O_3 for comparison, calculated with XTANT-3. The peak values of PbS and ITO fall within the range typical for metals and are comparable to that of elemental Pb, indicating efficient energy redistribution before lattice heating. By contrast, the conductivity in CdTe and CdS is substantially lower and nearly temperature-independent above 15,000 K, suggesting more spatially confined energy deposition under identical irradiation conditions.

To our knowledge, no published data exist for the electronic heat capacity, electronic heat conductivity, or electron–phonon coupling parameter in CdTe, PbS, or ITO as functions of electron temperature in the range relevant to ultrafast laser excitation. Available thermodynamic data in the literature, such as those reported in [70] for CdTe, address the lattice heat capacity as a function of ionic temperature up to ~ 1000 K within equilibrium lattice-based approaches; these are physically distinct from the electronic quantities plotted in figures 2–3, which span electron temperatures up to 20,000 K, and a direct quantitative comparison is therefore not possible.

3.2. Ultrafast damage in the bulk

We find the phase transition thresholds in a sequence of simulations varying the irradiation dose from 0.1 to 2.0 eV atom^{-1} , in steps of 0.1 eV atom^{-1} . The atomic snapshots in figures 5–6 show the examples of the material response to below and above the threshold doses. CdTe disorders at the dose of ~ 0.4 – 0.5 eV atom^{-1} (figure 5), while PbS and ITO do so at ~ 0.2 – 0.3 eV atom^{-1} (figure 7) and ~ 0.3 – 0.4 eV atom^{-1} (figure 6), respectively. For each material, at doses above the corresponding threshold, the atomic lattice loses stability.

The melting observed at the near-threshold doses is thermal, induced by atomic heating via electron–phonon coupling. This can be established by a comparison with the Born–Oppenheimer (BO) simulation, which

excludes the electron–phonon coupling, and thus nonadiabatic heating of the atomic system (not shown) [71]. The BO simulations demonstrate that the nonthermal damage onsets at higher doses for each material (table 1).

The atomic heating via electron–phonon coupling in non-BO simulations varies with the material; see the example of the equilibration of the electronic and atomic temperatures in figure 8. In ITO, the coupling parameter reaches its peak of $\sim 2.5 \times 10^{17}$ W/(m³K) at ~ 1 ps after the pulse, when the electronic temperature is still relatively high, and the atomic temperature is also close to its maximum [72], while in PbS and CdTe, the coupling parameter reaches its maximum around 4 ps post-irradiation. Afterwards, the coupling parameter decreases with a decrease in the electronic temperature [69].

In summary, CdTe appears to be more resistant to ultrafast irradiation than the other two materials under study, and comparable to CdS [73], but with slower phase transition dynamics, which is consistent with Te being heavier than S.

Table 1. Thermal and nonthermal phase transition threshold doses in bulk CdTe, PbS, and ITO calculated with XTANT-3.

Material	Calculated threshold dose (eV/atom)	
	non-BO simulations (thermal melting)	BO simulations (non- thermal melting)
CdTe	0.4–0.5	1.0
PbS	0.2–0.3	0.9
ITO	0.3–0.4	0.8

As shown in figure 9, in CdTe, at the dose of 0.4 eV atom⁻¹, the Te mean displacement saturates at ~ 0.6 Å, while the Cd atoms continue to move, demonstrating a diffusive (liquid-like) behavior. A similar behavior is observed in ITO (displacement of In and Sn atoms tends to plateau while it keeps increasing for O) at deposited doses between 0.3 eV atom⁻¹ and 0.6 eV atom⁻¹. This behavior is characteristic of transient superionic states—materials simultaneously exhibiting one solid and another liquid sublattice [41, 42, 74].

It is interesting to note that the superionic-like state in CdTe (in contrast to In₂O₃ and ITO) occurs at ~ 20 ps, where the electronic and atomic temperatures are almost equilibrated (cf figure 8), suggesting that the formation of this state is thermal, not triggered by the changes in the interatomic potential induced by high electronic temperatures.

As the radiation dose increases, the mean displacement of all species tends to equal, indicating that the materials reach complete melting in all sublattices.

In response to irradiation, the band gap in CdTe and PbS shrinks with an increase in the dose (figure 10). As is typical for ionic materials, the threshold dose for atomic disorder is lower than the threshold dose for the complete band gap collapse [75]. Interestingly, despite the previously discussed higher radiation resistance of CdTe, the dependence of bandgap shrinkage with radiation dose is comparable in both materials (figure 10): at doses around 0.4 eV atom⁻¹, the band gaps of both CdTe and PbS transiently contract to approximately 1 eV. A complete band gap collapse requires doses above 0.6–0.7 eV atom⁻¹. Thus, XTANT-3 calculations predict that, similar to CdS [73], these materials may transiently form semiconducting or metallic states, depending on the

Figure 8. Electronic temperature and atomic temperature (top panels) and time-resolved electron–ion coupling parameter (bottom panels) in CdTe at 0.5 eV atom^{-1} , PbS at 0.3 eV atom^{-1} , and ITO at 0.4 eV atom^{-1} — each at its respective thermal damage threshold. In ITO, coupling peaks at $\sim 2.5 \times 10^{17} \text{ W/(m}^3 \text{ K)}$ within $\sim 1 \text{ ps}$ after the pulse; in CdTe and PbS the peak is reached at $\sim 4 \text{ ps}$. The earlier equilibration in ITO compared to CdTe reflects ITO’s larger coupling.

Figure 9. Mean atomic displacement as a function of time for each element in bulk CdTe (left), PbS (centre), and ITO (right) at near thermal damage threshold dose (top row) and at 1.0 eV atom^{-1} (bottom row). A saturating curve indicates solid-like vibrations; a continuously growing one indicates liquid-like state. In CdTe at 0.4 eV atom^{-1} Te saturates ($\sim 0.6 \text{ \AA}$) while Cd continues to grow, and in ITO the In and Sn displacements plateau while O keeps increasing; these are the quantitative signatures of the transient superionic states. At 1.0 eV atom^{-1} all species continuously displace, indicating complete melting in all sublattices.

dose. Particularly in CdTe, the results suggest that the band gap may transiently be tuned even at doses below the phase transition threshold.

Figure 11 shows that, as in CdS [73], the band gap collapse in CdTe takes place mainly via lowering of the conduction band. This indicates that the electrons in the conduction band merge with the valence band holes due to energy levels shifting and lose their energy, consequently instigating the nonthermal acceleration of the atoms [40]. This one-sided collapse from above is consistent with different symmetry characters of conduction band minimum (Γ_6) and valence band maximum (Γ_8) of CdTe [76]. In PbS, by contrast, the band gap shrinks due to the widening of both the conduction and valence bands, similar to irradiated diamond [51]; this symmetric response reflects the centrosymmetric rocksalt structure of PbS [77], in which electronic excitation modifies states on both sublattices more equally, shifting both band edges outward. In ITO, the first response to irradiation is a destabilisation of the shallow Sn donor levels located below the conduction band bottom, which

begin to descend further below the conduction band minimum at doses around 0.2 eV atom⁻¹, while above 0.5 eV atom⁻¹, the band gap fully collapses.

Transition to the disordered state in CdTe and ITO is accompanied by the pressure turning negative, see figure 12. This indicates that the density of these materials in liquid states is higher than that of the respective crystalline states. Similar formation of a high-density liquid state after irradiation was predicted in silicon [51] and CdS [73]. In contrast, PbS is expected to expand with melting.

3.3. Long-time relaxation in the bulk

To estimate the stability of the predicted states and the effects of possible damage recovery in the studied materials, we simulated deposited doses up to 6 eV atom^{-1} , allowing for material cooling to the room temperature via a Berendsen thermostat (characteristic cooling time of 1 ps). By the end of these simulations, the atomic temperatures reach room temperature (figure 13). Upon cooling, the mean displacements of the species in the three materials saturate (figure 14). This suggests that the superionic behavior observed in CdTe and ITO (see section 3.2) is a transient state, and materials resolidify.

Accounting for material cooling increases the damage threshold doses. In CdTe, at irradiation doses up to $\sim 1.9 \text{ eV atom}^{-1}$, the band gap first collapses, as discussed in the previous section, but opens again with material cooling and recrystallization, returning to the original value. The same behavior is observed in PbS at doses below $\sim 1.0 \text{ eV atom}^{-1}$. In both materials the band gap reaches an equilibrium value ($E_{\text{gap}} \sim 1.0 \text{ eV}$ in CdTe and $E_{\text{gap}} \sim 0.8 \text{ eV}$ in PbS) at all doses above the threshold of 2.1 eV atom^{-1} in CdTe and 2.2 eV atom^{-1} in PbS. In a narrow region of doses, the created state has band gap values in between those of the crystalline and stable amorphous phases (figure 15). This suggests that irradiation with ultrashort pulses may be used in material processing to tune the band gap to some degree by tailoring the radiation parameters of the laser pulse.

In ITO, based on the band structure evolution, the band gap recovers to some extent up to doses around 2.2 eV atom^{-1} , but the material remains metallic after equilibration at all doses above this value (figure 16).

To access the evolving atomic structure in experiments, ultrafast photon or electron diffraction is often employed. Calculated powder diffraction patterns of CdTe irradiated with the dose of 1.0 eV atom^{-1} for the probe photon wavelength of 1.54 \AA (figure 17) show that by 1 ps , most of the crystalline peaks are no longer observable but return almost completely as the material cools down and relaxes to equilibrium, suggesting a high degree of recrystallization and confirming the high radiation-resistance of the material.

In ITO and PbS, even though at low doses, only the diffraction peaks at small angles return with relaxation, while the long-range order is lost—the materials do not recover to the extent observed in CdTe, likely due to the presence of light elements in the lattice.

3.4. Thin layer and surfaces

We have additionally modelled the effects of irradiation on thin layers of the studied materials. The threshold dose for phase transition is lower for each material in this form (table 2) compared to that in the bulk (cf

Figure 15. Time evolution band gap in CdTe (left) and PbS (right) for doses between 1.2 and 2.5 eV atom⁻¹, simulated with cooling ($\tau = 1$ ps). Below ~ 1.9 eV atom⁻¹ (CdTe) and ~ 1.0 eV atom⁻¹ (PbS) the band gap fully recovers to the crystalline value upon recrystallisation. Above 2.1 eV atom⁻¹ (CdTe) and 2.2 eV atom⁻¹ (PbS), the band gap converges to a dose-independent equilibrium value (~ 1.0 eV and ~ 0.8 eV, respectively), characteristic of a stable amorphous phase. The narrow intermediate dose range, where the gap settles between these two limits, represents the window in which ultrashort pulses can be used to tune the band gap without reaching the fully amorphous end-state.

Figure 16. Time-resolved energy levels in ITO at 1.5, 2.2, and 4.0 eV atom⁻¹ simulated with cooling via thermostat ($\tau = 1$ ps); valence band (VB), band gap (BG), and conduction band (CB) labelled. At 1.5 eV atom⁻¹ the final band gap is not fully collapsed; at and above 2.2 eV atom⁻¹, the CB and VB merge irreversibly, and the material remains metallic at all higher doses.

table 1). This is a consequence of the thin layer expansion, which destabilizes the atomic lattice, thereby lowering the damage threshold.

At doses above the ablation threshold (table 2) S and O, the most volatile species, are emitted from PbS and ITO surfaces, respectively. Also, in ITO, Sn-O aggregates are emitted (see figures 18–20). Interestingly, even though cadmium diffuses more readily within the bulk CdTe (cf figure 9), tellurium, the heavier element, is preferentially emitted from the surface (figures 18 and 21), suggesting its lower surface tension.

It is worth noting that the emission of atoms from the surface occurs at the timescale of tens of picoseconds in all studied materials at near-threshold doses (figures 18–20). It indicates thermal emission taking place after electron–ion temperature equilibration. We also envision that the timescale of the emission predicted may be validated in future dedicated experiments.

The band gap in CdTe and ITO thin layers (figure 22) shrinks to lower values compared to bulk materials irradiated with the same dose (cf figure 11). However, the opposite is observed in PbS, which is consistent with the expansion observed in the layer (cf figure 20) and the pressure profile calculated for the material (cf figure 12). It is in good agreement with the experimental reports on the effects of PbS films thickness on the optical properties of the material [78].

3.5. Damage threshold fluence

Having evaluated the damage threshold doses in the studied materials, they can be converted into the incoming fluence threshold [51]. Such a conversion assumes normal photon incidence, no nonlinear effects, no particle and energy transport in the sample, and no electron or photon emission from the surface.

The bulk threshold fluences in CdTe, PbS, ITO, and CdS for comparison, are shown in figure 23, using EPICS2023 photoabsorption cross sections for the conversion. The damage thresholds are relatively close to one another in all the studied photovoltaic materials, except for different sudden jumps due to different ionization potentials of various shells in different elements. The low damage threshold calculated for ITO is

Figure 17. Simulated x-ray powder diffraction patterns ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) in CdTe (left), PbS (centre), and ITO (right) at 1.0 eV atom^{-1} with cooling ($\tau = 1 \text{ ps}$), shown at six time steps from -200 fs to 30 ps (15 ps in the case of ITO); atomic snapshots are shown as insets. In CdTe the Bragg peaks vanish by $\sim 1 \text{ ps}$ but return almost completely by 30 ps , confirming a high degree of recrystallisation and radiation resistance. In PbS and ITO only low-angle peaks recover, and long-range order is lost — consistent with the larger residual atomic displacements retained after cooling in these materials. These patterns could be directly measured in a time-resolved x-ray or ultrafast electron diffraction experiment.

Table 2. Melting and ablation threshold doses in CdTe, PbS, and ITO thin layers calculated with XTANT-3.

Material	Phase transition threshold (eV/atom)	Ablation threshold (eV/atom)
CdTe	0.3	0.6
PbS	0.2	0.4
ITO	0.2	0.4

qualitatively supported by the experimental observation in [79]. These estimates may guide future experiments and application of XUV/x-ray-irradiation of the photovoltaic materials studied.

4. Conclusions

We simulated the response of CdTe, PbS and ITO using the combined code XTANT-3, tracing simultaneously nonequilibrium electron kinetics, nonadiabatic electron–phonon coupling, and nonthermal phase transitions. It is found that CdTe transiently disorders at irradiation doses above $\sim 0.4\text{--}0.5 \text{ eV per atom}$, while ITO and PbS disorder at $\sim 0.3\text{--}0.4 \text{ eV atom}^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.2\text{--}0.3 \text{ eV atom}^{-1}$, respectively. The damage threshold fluence versus XUV/x-ray photon energy is also estimated for all studied materials (and CdS for comparison).

The lowest damage threshold corresponds to thermal melting induced by the electron–phonon coupling and heating of the atomic lattice. All the materials also exhibit nonthermal melting at higher doses: CdTe at 0.8 eV atom^{-1} , PbS at 0.9 eV atom^{-1} , and ITO at 1 eV atom^{-1} . CdTe and PbS may transiently form semiconducting melted states in the dose intervals between 0.5 and 0.7 eV atom^{-1} while turning into metallic liquid at higher doses. CdTe and ITO transiently exhibit superionic states with coexisting solid and liquid sublattices.

The threshold doses increase if energy sinks from the samples and corresponding recrystallization are taken into account. CdTe appears to have the highest recrystallization degree among the studied materials. Below the threshold dose of 1.5 eV atom^{-1} , the band gap of each material returns to its original value. With the increase of the dose, the cooled state becomes more amorphous, with correspondingly smaller band gap until an equilibrium value is reached. The results suggest that femtosecond lasers may be useful in tuning the band gap of photovoltaic semiconductors.

At the deposited doses of 0.6 eV atom^{-1} in CdTe, and 0.4 eV atom^{-1} in PbS and ITO, material ablation from the surface occurs, respectively emitting Te, S, and O/Sn-O aggregates at the characteristic timescale of $\sim 10 \text{ ps}$.

The presented results suggest a few unique features in these materials. First, the superionic state in ITO is nonthermal in origin (similar to reports on alumina and water [41, 42, 74]) whereas in CdTe it emerges at ~ 20

ps when electronic and atomic temperatures have already equilibrated, identifying it as thermal in origin. Second, ITO exhibits a two-stage band gap collapse: Sn donor levels destabilise before the intrinsic In–O gap is perturbed, followed by full closure above $\sim 0.5 \text{ eV atom}^{-1}$, in contrast to the continuous gap closure observed in CdTe, PbS, CdS [73], and diamond [51]. Third, CdTe and ITO densify upon melting as their open structures

collapse to higher-coordination liquids, while PbS expands conventionally, consistent with the absence of a denser polymorph in the rocksalt structure. Fourth, although Cd is the more mobile species in the bulk, Te is preferentially emitted from the surface, consistent with the lower surface tension of the elemental Te [80].

The results may guide future XFEL experiments by identifying potential radiation-induced damage and electronic modifications in ITO-based instrumentation, such as ITO-coated glass substrates used in *in situ* electrochemical cells applied for x-ray studies [43–46]. It enables distinguishing substrate-related artifacts and optimizing the exploitation of ITO's photovoltaic and electronic properties to enhance electrochemical performance. The electronic structure response of CdTe to high x-ray doses may inform detector calibration and performance correction under high intensities. Our results indicate that femtosecond laser excitation can be employed to precisely tailor the electronic properties of photovoltaic materials.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability statement

The code XTANT-3 used to simulate irradiation effects is available from [47]. Calculated electronic thermal parameters (electronic heat capacity, heat conductivity, and electron–phonon coupling) are publicly available from the following URL: https://github.com/N-Medvedev/XTANT-3_coupling_data.

Author contributions

Aldo Artímez Peña 0009-0006-8225-5534

Conceptualization (equal), Formal analysis (equal), Investigation (equal), Methodology (supporting), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal)

Nikita Medvedev 0000-0003-0491-1090

Conceptualization (equal), Formal analysis (equal), Investigation (equal), Methodology (lead), Software (lead), Supervision (lead), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (lead)

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